

Thermogravimetric Analysis with a Heated Quartz Crystal Microbalance

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Abstract—Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) with an SC-cut quartz crystal microbalance (QCM) was demonstrated at temperatures in the range from 20 °C to 450 °C. A measurement system was built around a crystal sensor head that was mounted in a small tube furnace. Changes in third-overtone C-mode frequencies of the crystal were measured during thermally activated decomposition and combustion of a poly(methyl methacrylate) (PMMA) film with an initial mass of approximately 6 μg , and corresponding changes in mass Δm were estimated through the use of the Sauerbrey equation. Noise and drift in frequencies and associated Δm were determined through least-squares fitting and compared with commercially available high-resolution conventional TGA systems. The microbalance-based TGA (μ -TGA) system is found to have one to two orders of magnitude lower noise than high-resolution TGA at temperatures below 200 °C and to have at least an order of magnitude lower drift over the entire measured temperatures. However, increasing temperature dependence of crystal frequencies at elevated temperatures and noise in temperature measurements lead to noise in the determination of temperature-dependent mass above 400 °C that is comparable in magnitude to that of high-resolution TGA. Enhancements in performance of μ -TGA depend primarily on the implementation of reliable piezoelectric resonators with low temperature dependence over the entire measured range.

I. INTRODUCTION

Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) is widely used to characterize materials through the measurement of mass changes arising from decomposition, oxidation, corrosion, moisture adsorption/desorption, and gas evolution during heating. However, TGA is impractical for many applications where the required mass of the material of interest is unavailable or prohibitively expensive. Quartz crystal microbalances (QCMs) offer an alternate approach to thermogravimetric analysis that takes advantage of the high sensitivity of resonant acoustic frequencies to thermally induced changes in mass deposited on the surface of a crystal. This approach has been pursued in a number of studies of thin films at cryogenic temperatures, with mass deposited through condensation of vapor onto a QCM. [1]–[3]. The application of crystal microbalances to thermogravimetric measurements (μ -TGA) at temperatures well above ambient temperatures (the range of conventional TGA) has been pursued only in the past decade. The challenges of such measurements are substantial and include uncertainties arising from the temperature dependence of acoustic velocities, higher crystal damping at elevated temperatures, analyte

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damping, irreversible changes in crystal-defect anelasticity, temperature-dependent interference of spurious modes (“activity dips”), temperature limit of quartz associated with the phase transition at 573 °C, limited availability of piezoelectric materials that operate reliably at higher temperatures, and temperature limits of commercially available crystal-sensor heads. Thanner *et al.* [4] presented an initial demonstration of elevated-temperature μ -TGA involving the evaporation of oil from the surface of a GaPO₄ resonator during heating to 720 °C. Mansfield *et al.* [5] more extensively explored the application of μ -TGA through measurements on a number of demonstration materials, including two-component mixtures. [5] In that study, measurements of AT-cut QCM frequencies were performed at ambient temperatures after each of a series of heatings of the crystal. Thus, challenges associated with high-temperature QCM operation were avoided at the expense of greatly increased measurement period. This approach of ambient-temperature frequency measurements was also employed by Seby and Mansfield [6] to characterize thermal decomposition and combustion of polymer-stabilized gold nanoparticles.

In this report, we describe the design of a μ -TGA system that provides continuous measurements up to 450 °C. This system is based on an SC-cut crystal and a crystal-sensor head that was originally designed for monitoring the deposition of thin films at elevated temperatures. The performance of this system is explored through demonstration measurements on poly(methyl methacrylate) (PMMA).

II. EXPERIMENTAL TECHNIQUE

A commercially manufactured QCM sensor head (Conatec Tempe500 [7]) with a nominal temperature limit of 500 °C was mounted in a small tube furnace with a bore of 5 cm, as shown in Fig 1. Measurements were performed in air with no introduced flow. Temperature ramps up to 450 °C were controlled through the use of a thermocouple and ramp sequencer built in to the furnace. The nominal ramp rate was set to 2 °C/min. Temperatures of the QCM were determined with a Type-K thermocouple mounted in the sensor head, in order to minimize temperature differences between the crystal and thermocouple. The temperature of the sensor head lagged behind that of the furnace thermocouple during heating, and this difference decreased at higher temperatures. As a result of this, the ramp rate of the crystal increased with temperature

up to 200 °C and, then, remained approximately constant at 2.2 °C/min \pm 0.2 °C/min above 200 °C.

Fig. 1. Experimental hardware, including QCM sensor head and surrounding tube furnace.

To excite a resonant vibrational mode of the specimen, a sinusoidal tone burst with a duration of 1.5 ms was applied to the electrodes at a frequency close to resonance. Freely decaying vibrations of the specimen following excitation were detected through piezoelectrically induced voltages on the electrodes, and the time-dependent in-phase and out-of-phase components of this signal were derived through analogue electronics (with a RITEC RAM-5000 [7]). The resonant frequency was determined in real time from the point of maximum slope of the phase of a complex fast Fourier transform (FFT) of the decaying in-phase and out-of-phase components. The inverse quality factor Q^{-1} was determined in the time domain from the rate of exponential decay of the signal magnitude determined from the phase-detected components.

The focus of the measurements was on the third C-mode resonance of the crystal, which is less sensitive to contact with the sensor head than the poorly trapped fundamental C mode. The measurements of frequency, Q^{-1} , and temperature were acquired at 8 s intervals and averaged in sequential sets of three.

III. SPECIMEN

An SC-cut quartz with crystal orientation $\theta=33^{\circ}57'50''$ and $\phi=24^{\circ}00'00''$ (following standard notation for the angles [9]) was employed for the mass sensor. The crystal was plano-convex with a curvature of 2-diopter and a diameter of 14 mm.

SC-cut quartz has several characteristics that made it attractive for this initial implementation of μ -TGA below 500 °C. It has excellent stability and reproducibility in heated environments, and the temperature dependence of its C-mode frequencies up to 300 °C is much lower than that of other conventional cuts of quartz. [10]

The crystal was preheated to 450 °C and cooled to ambient temperatures. Then, a PMMA film with a molecular mass of 1.2 kg/mole was spin-coated onto one face of the crystal from an acetone solution. Following deposition and drying at ambient temperature, PMMA within \sim 3 mm of the edge of the crystal was removed by wiping with an acetone-saturated cotton swab, in order to eliminate the film in areas where the crystal was in contact with the sensor head.

IV. RESULTS

Measurements of the frequency f_{C3} of the third C-mode overtone during heating of the crystal with PMMA present are shown in Fig. 2(a), along with reference measurements during a subsequent heating of the crystal without PMMA. The frequencies with PMMA are \sim 4.6 kHz below the reference curve near ambient temperatures and approach the reference curve as the PMMA leaves the surface during heating. Figure 2(b) shows corresponding measurements of the inverse quality factor Q^{-1} during heating with and without PMMA. As the temperature rises, Q^{-1} rises substantially above the reference and then drops back to the reference curve as the PMMA leaves the crystal. Steps in Q^{-1} over relatively narrow temperature ranges also are present, and these are attributed to variations in contact between the crystal and the sensor head, as described below.

The difference between the two frequency curves in Fig. 2(a) are shown in Fig. 3(a). Corresponding changes in mass Δm of PMMA are estimated through the use of the Sauerbrey equation, [11]

$$\Delta m = -\frac{\Delta f_{C3} A (C_{ij} \rho_q)^{1/2}}{2n f_0^2}, \quad (1)$$

where C_{ij} is the effective elastic constant, ρ_q is the volume mass density of quartz, n is the overtone number, f_0 is the fundamental frequency, and A is the active area of the resonator. Considering that A cannot be accurately known without characterizing the vibrational trapping of the resonator, it would be more natural to express mass changes in units of mass per unit area ($\Delta m/A$). However, for the purpose of comparing the capabilities of μ -TGA with conventional TGA in this report, it is useful to present estimates of Δm without area normalization. The value of A is approximated as that of the center electrode of the resonator, 0.32 cm². The uncertainty in this value is considered to be a factor of two. The temperature-dependent Δm estimated in this way is shown in Fig. 3(b). The PMMA mass was equal to approximately 6.4 μ g at ambient temperatures and dropped to zero during heating in the range of 250 °C to 400 °C. The temperature range of \sim 250 °C to \sim 400 °C over which the PMMA leaves

Fig. 2. Frequency and corresponding Q^{-1} of the third C-mode overtone during heating with and without a PMMA film on the surface of the crystal.

the crystal is consistent with expectations from published TGA measurements of PMMA. [12]

Noise in the measured Δf_{C3} versus temperature was determined by least-squares fitting of the data of Fig. 3(a) to cubic polynomials over 50 °C temperature ranges. The standard deviations σ in Δf_{C3} relative to these fits are listed in Table I, along with those of similar fits to values of Δm in Fig. 3(b). The estimated factor-of-two uncertainty in A , mentioned above, leads to a factor-of-two uncertainty in the values of σ of Δm in this table.

TABLE I
STANDARD DEVIATIONS σ IN MEASURED Δf_{C3} AND Δm VERSUS TEMPERATURE RELATIVE TO LEAST-SQUARES CUBIC-POLYNOMIAL FITS OF THE DATA OVER LIMITED TEMPERATURE RANGES.

Temperature range (°C)	σ of Δf_{C3} (Hz)	σ of Δm (μg)
20 to 70	1.0	0.0014
150 to 200	1.8	0.0025
300 to 350	21	0.030
400 to 450	62	0.087

Increased noise in the measurements at elevated temper-

Fig. 3. (a) Difference of the two curves of frequency f_{C3} versus temperature in Fig. 2 and (b) corresponding changes in PMMA mass on the crystal, estimated from the Sauerbrey equation, Eq. 1.

atures does not arise primarily from an increase in phase noise associated with higher Q^{-1} . This can be seen by noting that the σ of Δf_{C3} increases monotonically with temperature, while Q^{-1} goes through a maximum on heating with PMMA present (Fig. 2(b)) and is higher at intermediate temperatures (320 °C to 350 °C) than it is at the highest temperatures. The noise in Δf_{C3} versus temperature is understood to arise primarily from scatter in temperature measurements. At 425 °C, the slope of f_{C3} versus temperature (Fig. 2(a)) of the crystal is ~ 66 ppm/°C. Therefore, a standard deviation of 62 Hz in Δf_{C3} at this temperature (Table I) corresponds to a standard deviation in temperature measurements of 0.06 °C.

The reproducibility of the frequency versus temperature was explored through a series of measurements during repeated heatings from ambient temperatures to ~ 450 °C without analyte on the crystal surface. Five heatings were performed at random intervals over a period of sixteen days without removing the crystal from the sensor head. Figure 4 shows differences in the frequencies relative to the first heating.

The maximum drift in frequencies is less than 35 Hz below 200 °C and increases to ~ 300 Hz at the highest temperatures. If such drift in the crystal frequencies occurred during μ -TGA measurements, the corresponding systematic drift in Δm (determined through Eq. 1) would be $0.05 \mu\text{g}$ below 200 °C and $0.4 \mu\text{g}$ at 450 °C. However, the data indicate that drift is much less over a period of one day, especially at the higher temperatures. The two data sets acquired on the fourth day after the first heating show no clear difference in frequencies at the highest temperatures, within the uncertainties introduced by the random noise of the measurements, and this is also the case for high-temperature frequencies measured on the fifteenth and sixteenth days. Below 250 °C, the greatest differences between frequencies measured over the period of a single day are ~ 20 Hz. Therefore, the data support the conclusion that reference measurements taken within a day of analyte measurements are subject to drift on the order of 20 Hz, if the crystal is not removed from the sensor head. This corresponds to drift in Δm on the order of $0.03 \mu\text{g}$. Additional measurements (not shown) of f_{C3} at ambient temperatures with repeated removal and reinsertion of the crystal in the sensor head showed a standard deviation of 7 Hz.

Additional systematic shifts in f_{C3} were observed in measurements on a second PMMA film. Abrupt shifts in f_{C3} on the order of 10 Hz or less occurred at temperatures where shifts in Q^{-1} (such as those shown in Fig. 2(b)) occurred. As mentioned above, such systematic shifts are attributed to variations in mechanical contact between the resonator and sensor head. Specifically, thermally accelerated plastic creep is understood to occur in the metallic leaf springs that provide electrical contact with resonator electrodes. Evidence for creep is provided by an observed reduction in the height of the springs after heating to 450 °C. Variations in contact arising from oxidation of the springs may also have been a factor in earlier measurements, but this potential problem was addressed by evaporating a gold film on the springs.

To provide an initial evaluation of the relative advantages of ramped μ -TGA, in its current implementation, we compare the results presented here with conventional TGA. From an inspection of manufacturers' specifications of commercial TGA systems, we find that systems capable of measuring the smallest changes in mass have resolutions on the order of $0.03 \mu\text{g}$, noise on the order of $0.1 \mu\text{g}$, and drift, during a ramped TGA measurement, on the order of $1 \mu\text{g}$. From Table I and the estimated factor of two for the uncertainties of σ of Δm , our values of Δm of PMMA determined from μ -TGA can be seen to have a noise level that is 20 to 80 times smaller than the noise of high-resolution TGA below 200 °C. However, above 400 °C, the noise in our system was comparable in magnitude to that of high-resolution TGA. Our measurements of drift in crystal frequencies indicate that the corresponding drift in Δm can be expected to be at least an order of magnitude smaller than high-resolution TGA over the entire measured range of temperatures, if reference measurements are acquired within a day of analyte measurements. With respect to these comparisons, one should note that accurate

Fig. 4. Differences between third-overtone C-mode frequencies measured during five heatings of the crystal (without analyte on the surface). Measurements during the first heating are subtracted from those of subsequent heatings. To reduce random scatter at the higher temperatures, measurements were averaged in sequential sets corresponding to temperature intervals of $13 \text{ }^\circ\text{C} \pm 2 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ above 100 °C. The days in which the measurements were taken are listed in the legend, with the first heating defined to be on Day 0.

absolute measurement of mass is not generally of interest in thermogravimetric analysis. In fact, TGA measurements are often reported in terms of fractional mass changes versus temperature, which conveys all of the relevant information about thermally activated kinetics. Therefore, uncertainties in absolute mass determinations in μ -TGA, associated primarily with uncertainties in the active area A of the crystal, are not a significant limitation of this approach.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This work provides an initial demonstration of a continuously ramped μ -TGA system employing an SC-cut quartz crystal, a commercial sensor head, a tube furnace, and a tone-burst ultrasonic measurement system. Thermally activated decomposition and combustion of a PMMA film with an initial mass of $\sim 6 \mu\text{g}$ has been monitored during heating to 450 °C. The noise and drift in the measurements have been compared with the highest-resolution commercial TGA systems currently available. This implementation of μ -TGA is found to offer substantial advantages with respect to noise below 200 °C and drift over the entire measured temperature range. It is found to offer no significant advantage with respect to noise above 400 °C.

Limitations of the μ -TGA system, in its current form, are associated primarily with the temperature dependence of the resonant frequencies of quartz, noise in temperature measurements, and variations in crystal contact with the sensor head. None of these are considered to present fundamental obstacles to implementing μ -TGA with substantial advantages over conventional TGA in the temperature range up to ~ 500 °C. A reduction in temperature dependence of

the frequencies is the most substantial challenge, and this challenge is shared with numerous other high-temperature sensing applications. The ultimate temperature limit of quartz, associated with its 573 °C phase transition, also presents a substantial challenge with respect to implementing μ -TGA at temperatures more typical of conventional TGA. To address the issues of temperature dependence and upper-temperature limit of the crystal microbalance, our future work will include an exploration of the use of $\text{La}_3\text{Ga}_{5.5}\text{Ta}_{0.5}\text{O}_{14}$ (langatate), which offers advantages of simplified crystal growth, relative to some high-temperature piezoelectric materials, [13] and has been found to have relatively low temperature dependence up to 500 °C, in some crystal orientations. [14]

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